

AUTONOMY IN FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Annotation: This article is about characteristics to learner autonomy and independent learning process. An autonomous learner can make informed choices, set goals, and make decisions about how to succeed in his learning needs. Also, the **independent learner** takes responsibility for building and performing their learning, monitoring their progress toward accomplishing their learning goals and self-assess the outcomes of the learning process.

Key words: Independent study, an autonomous learner, process, take responsibility, independent, motivation, self-confidence

Independent study is a process, a method and a philosophy of education whereby a learner gains knowledge by his or her own attempts and develops the ability for enquiry and critical evaluation. Independent learning is a process in which development of values, attitudes, knowledge and skills are needed to make responsible decisions and teach students to take actions individually. Independent learning is promoted by creating study skills, which encourage student's motivation, curiosity, self-confidence and self-reliance; it is based on learners understanding their interests and the value of what they are learning.

Independent learning is a way or process of learning in which learners have control and ownership of their learning. They regulate, direct, and evaluate their learning and learn due to their actions. An autonomous learner can make informed choices, set goals, and make decisions about how to succeed in his learning needs. Also, the independent learner takes responsibility for building and performing their learning, monitoring their progress toward accomplishing their learning goals and self-assess the outcomes of the learning process. At Structural Learning, we have a certain interest in equipping disadvantaged students with the skills and techniques to move

their learning forward. When children turn into adults, they will have to control their studies independently. The demands of exams sometimes mean that schools focus their preparation on exam technique instead of the affective skills essential to becoming a lifelong learner.

Owning the right resources is one thing but having educational experiences that nurture these abilities is another paradigm altogether. Metacognitive practice including the skills of reflection and exam technique can be embedded into a rich educational experience. Society often sees education in terms of exam success but activities such as 'learning to learn' should be very much built into the day to day school life of a child. We are not talking about separate skills courses but rather incremental steps that are embedded into subjects that lead the student to take more ownership of their education. Independent learning can also be described as “learning strategy that fosters self-improvement through planned independent study by students under the guidance or supervision of an instructor, can include learning in partnership with another individual or as part of a small group, possible instructional methods used include: reading, viewing, and assigned questions” (Nathanson, 1984).

Many scholars have defined independent learning in various ways; thus, independent learning is a concept that has no universally agreed definition. Independent learning has been receiving tremendous interest from governments, industrialists, and academics in the advancement of higher learning education strategies, since it is capable of producing lifelong learners, skilled, and self-motivated people who are pivotal to the future of any nation. All definitions or concepts on independent learning are based on the learner taking control of their studies. Since the university students are adults, they are expected to achieve a balance between learning, work and their other attachments. For successful independent learning, the students must organize their learning through time and resources management, and prioritizing their tasks and structure of their schedule to achieve mutual balance between study and other activities.

A departure from dependent learning, independent learning is viewed as a tool that transforms education by enhancing many qualities such as the habits of mind that improve critical, analytical and reflective thinking skills, and also improve and shape students' personality by enhancing self-reliance, self-confidence, and critical thinking skills (Najera, et al., Nd). All academic learning processes are supported by more than one academic skill. Academic skills are mainly composed of reading, writing and study skills, thus, any independent learning should encompass these skills. Therefore, it is important for an independent learner to develop these skills in order to achieve a successful independent learning outcome.

Learners who take an active role in their learning:

- ~ take responsibility for their own learning
- ~ evaluate their own learning
- ~ are hardworking
- ~ are always well prepared
- ~ are motivated
- ~ work independently
- ~ develop learning strategies
- ~ set their own learning goals
- ~ define the ways to achieve the goals
- ~ always seek for further information and study on their own
- ~ find different ways to improve their language skills

Autonomous learners take responsibility for their own learning. One of the most effective ways to help students take responsibility for their learning is through goal setting. When students set goals and achieve those goals, they build self-confidence and become more willing to try again.

An autonomous learner can evaluate their own learning Self-assessment is an efficient technique that helps you become more self-conscious. It echoes your current self-view by measuring your values, skills, and motivations.

The goal of organizing your time is to help become aware of how to use your time.

Developing and planning for blocks of study time in a typical week is a useful way of getting things done. Keeping in mind some difficult material may require more time than others. Determining a place free from distraction where you can maximize your concentration like the library.

Used Literature

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